

Music on the Wrong Side of Art

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ABSTRACT: Music and dance follow human development. The beginnings of music spontaneously hit various kinds of behaving that accompanied free movement (dance) within the community. In addition to relaxation and enjoyment, music has often been used in some undesirable behavior forms by today's standards. Music encourages soldiers to raise the morale and willingness of the army to win. This act intimidated opponents—the first example of using musical instruments in the best-selling Christian book of the Bible (Jericho). Today, music is wide-ranging and classified into different categories; this happens freely in other performers who may encounter hate speech. Music is used as a means of provoking and intimidating certain target groups. Depending on the country and the area, we come across numerous music examples on the "wrong side." The examination refers to how to use music that should inspire and raise the values of human beings in a strange way that causes fear, panic, hiding, discrimination in some groups. These people are primarily in the minority: nationality, religion, skin color, sexual orientation, or any other isolation and mockingly aggressive attitude towards selected people. Music began to use for ideological purposes during the French Revolution, and this firefighting practice spread to Europe in the 19th century. Music by manipulation became the music of hatred towards different and others. Beautiful and sublime, placed in the proper context, music can evoke strong emotions. The desired effect is achieved by the synergy of music and text, its persistent appearance within a particular ideology, and asocial.

KEYWORDS: prejudice, music, hatred, discrimination, misuse of music, the influence of music

1. Introduction

Synthesis of the essence and power of music can cause harmful products of the human mind. Ancient philosophers dealt with the question of the influence of music on the human mind. Music is ubiquitous in people's lives, whether it is the deliberate choice of a person or imposed by the media, corporations, or individuals.

Since its oldest history, music, sounds, and screaming have served as a means of communication. From today's primary means of communication, just as words can "hit" us and provoke negative emotions in us, sounds can cause the same symptoms. Music is an art and, as such, is primarily presented in a positive light and, among other things, serves people to help with relaxation, fun, etc. The fact is that music can have the opposite effect. People consciously or unconsciously resort to the theme that corresponds to their mental state at a certain point in time. In this paper, several problems have been investigated and solved: how music evokes negative emotions in listeners; why we listen to music that makes us sad or cries; how disturbing piece affects the perception of the situation and human emotions when watching movies; to what extent the lyrics negatively affect behavior and what messages they convey to us; how music can aggravate the mental state; music therapies; how inmates tortured prisoners with music; how piece affects mental health. With an impact on mental states, processes in the brain are represented by active or passive listening to music; they describe a negative impact on the physical condition, clearer hearing.

2. Prejudices and stereotypes

Prejudice is most often negative judgments about groups of people who share a common trait, so a warning about some of their negative characteristics should protect us from them. There are several different prejudices, such as those about people from other parts of the country,

about people of different professions, men or women, young or older, and they all have the same description all people based on one character in the group. Prejudice refers to a pre-adapted "Judgment" on something that a person does not know enough that the concept of prejudice is closely related to stereotypes, that is, generalizations.

Stereotypes represent the assignment of specific characteristics to people based on the group to which they belong. Prejudices and stereotypes encourage us not to connect with those according to whom we have negative prejudices, and we do not have the opportunity to understand that these prejudices are incorrect and cannot apply to whole groups of people.

Neither prejudice nor stereotypes are usually correct. People usually judge other people based on known data that is often incomplete, subjective and accurate. Even though experts have confirmed that people in the first assessments of people are wrong, this does not seem to prevent us from creating new stereotypes and prejudices.

In addition to affecting a person's self-esteem, prejudices regularly offend racial, sexual, religious, political and many other individual traits.

One of the accepted definitions of stereotypes is: "A standardized mental image accepted by members of a particular group and represents a simplified opinion, biased attitude or non-critical assessment" (Poljak 2018). This definition clearly reflects the common belief that stereotypes are accurate and lead to negative generalization. This popular opinion is most often wrong. Prejudice and stereotypes necessarily lead to discrimination against other individuals or groups. Discrimination can be defined as the unfair treatment of individuals belonging to a particular social group (Bordalo et al. 2014).

2.1. Prejudice is dangerous

Precisely because they often result in discrimination, unjustified, harmful behavior towards group members, simply because they belong to that group, prejudice can indeed be dangerous. Moreover, they are often the source of many conflicts. Experts believe that culture (parents, community, and media) deliberately or unfoundedly teaches us to attribute negativity and characteristics to different people.

2.2. Modern prejudice

A more recent term in psychology, but above all present in society, is modern prejudice. It is about unbiased behavior in front of others while maintaining discrimination. It would also mean that prejudices were not eradicated but only became more secret. People have become more cautious in expressing their prejudices, but they are very present. In races, this phenomenon is called modern racism, which means that people have learned to hide prejudices not to be called racist, and when the situation is "safe," their prejudices come to light. As Albert Einstein said "It's harder to break prejudice than an atom."

3. Music as a medium

The development of recording techniques in the second half of the 20th century revolutionizes music availability. Most people have access to all kinds of music 24 hours a day at the touch of a button. The flip side of the coin is that people often take it for granted because of this facilitated approach to music in the Western world. Music is a compelling medium, and there has been an attempt to control its use in some societies. However, it has a strong influence at the social group level because it allows communication that no longer needs words, encompasses the meanings and meanings that the group shares, and encourages the development and well-being of individual, group, cultural and national subjects.

On an individual level, music is powerful because it can provoke multiple reactions - psychological, movement reactions, mood swings, emotional, cognitive (cognitive), and behavioral (at the behavioral level). Several things can cause such a significant effect on such

a wide range of human functions. Since the brain processes music more than once, it is difficult to predict some piece's impact on the individual accurately. Music is also used to provoke appropriate behavior in groups of susceptible, vulnerable people and improve people's quality of life who cannot help by medical or pharmaceutical means.

3.1. Music Options

Music is art expressed by sound; art, knowledge, or skill of combining sounds within the sound system; the same product of the composer's sounds: composition, structure, song - a synonym that music uses in most languages. There are many different definitions of music, depending on the accent of its societies: meaning, Plato (Harnden 2014), individual experience (ability to distinguish tones, Ptolemy (Poljak 2018), sensibility (expression of feelings by techniques), within. Structure (nature of sound design, Kleonik (Poljak 2018), tonal word, proper singing, music (Renaissance), and various philosophers; definitions of its meaning, at the latest.

3.2.1. Aesthetics and music.

Theory (musicology), which explores the development of music, is associated with the very beginnings of human expression, especially in connection with cults, most often together with dance. In addition, music is associated with poetry, confirmed in the first sheet music systems and theoretical discussion of music. The social significance of music in prehistory, but partly in antiquity, the work of the musical society, magical ceremonies, ceremonies, and other events. Music is a compelling medium.

3.2. The power of music

Music can very strongly affect our feelings, mood, and behavior. Music can trace back centuries. Throughout history, the music theme was used for such different purposes as cheering before battle, putting babies to sleep, encouraging courtship, and following various ceremonies and important events throughout life. Music was used to trigger a riot, but also music can also shake a truce. Music is considered a powerful tool that the government seeks to control or even ban in some cultures. In Nazi Germany, music was carefully selected for public gatherings to produce appropriate patriotic sentiments. In the former USSR, the government banned Shostakovich's music. During the Cultural Revolution in China, Western music was declared decadent and forbidden. In Iran, strict restrictions were placed on certain types of music during the reign of Ayatollah Khomeini. Music is also used to provoke appropriate behavior in groups of susceptible, vulnerable people and improve people's quality of life who cannot help by medical or pharmaceutical means. In white-dominated South Africa, centers of African music were demolished, while musicians living in emigration continued to influence the world's stance against the prevailing white political regime with their music.

There is a lot of evidence that Western 'institutions' criticise rock music as well as its consequences. How powerful music is illustrated by the special attention paid to observing the influence of certain types of music and their possible excitement with antisocial or self-destructive behavior. Since music plays an important role in adolescence, older generations are constantly concerned about possible negative effects on the behavior of young people.

Listening to any music, in itself, is unlikely to provoke aggression, but in people who are already predisposed to violence and who have already taken the views expressed in the music in question, this may support a certain action. One study of listener perceptions found that only a few believe music really influences their behavior. Nevertheless, belonging to a particular youth music culture in some countries may increase the likelihood of psychiatric hospitalization.

Listeners of one culture often have difficulty understanding the feelings expressed by the music of another culture because the emotional expression is culturally determined. In most cultures, music has functions that are not only the fun and aesthetic enjoyment of the individual.

Music is actually an alternative means of communication between individuals and groups, although this communication may be limited to those who understand the specific meaning of the musical genre used. As an example, in Montreal when classical music was played on the subway, trying to convince young people that they should not stay there. The procedure was very effective. Music plays a role in most of our social institutions and religious ceremonies, for example, at birthdays, weddings and funerals, sports competitions, military events in some cases, music can be a powerful tool for change. It can play an important role in uniting and expressing solidarity in people who challenge social norms and actions. It can also be a powerful tool for maintaining the continuity and stability of society through folk music (folklore) and songs that talk about myths and legends and record important events. In our increasingly global society, folk music can be an important tool for preserving the identity of minority cultures

3.3. Impact of heavy and deadly metal music rock

By analyzing the influence of hard rock, heavy and death metal music, it is necessary to pay attention to a very important aspect of these types of music, which are song lyrics. In many songs it is very explicit according to topics such as sexual relations, violence, drug use and death. Heavy metal, whose numerous texts express dangerous and suicidal messages to adolescents in psychological development who are psychologically very vulnerable at that age, gave the greatest concern, given that this is when their upbringing begins.

The article of American pediatricians provides information about adolescents who show the consequences of frequently listening to songs whose lyrics are not appropriate for their age, and some of these consequences are: suicides, sexually transmitted diseases due to uneducatedness, unwanted pregnancy, self-harm, etc. Therefore, under the influence of listening to negative texts, mentally unstable adolescents without parental supervision will eventually begin to understand procedures such as rape, aggression, murder, etc., by normal behavior. Even the ancient philosopher Plato associated music with an "irrational", barbaric "part of the soul," arguing that music directly influences feelings long before reason can interpret whether it is a threat to content (Harnden 2014). What is negative about song slogans, Milos (1996) says, analyzing the lyrics of famous artists, only one of the slogans is: "Sex, drugs and rock 'n' roll are all your body needs."

Due to loud musical communication, people are difficult, so they are isolated from society. Although they are in a multitude of music lovers, they are preoccupied with their own thoughts that music affects, they have only physical contact with other people and are focused on performing on stage. Milos (1996) cites, for example, Frank Zappa (Poljak 2018), who staged puppets during the show and showed sexual intercourse with minors and animals, and Vincent Furnier (Milos 1996), who also used dolls and showed scenes of crippling the human body, as well as terrifying rituals of raping children and lifeless bodies.

What young people don't see, and may not know, is the fact that after the concert, some performers suffer terrible consequences caused by the use of LSD and other narcotic drugs. The music industry of hard rock, heavy and death metal music is subjected to frequent verbal attacks, mainly by parents, for its content (suicidal and inappropriate, vulgar messages ...) that are presented to the public, and therefore directly to children and young people. Milos (1996) points out that metal music peaked in the 20th century. We can not declare the nerdy genre completely negative. Depending on the mental state of the individual, so the data of Charles Manson (Harnden 2009) was recorded, who said that he found inspiration for the murders he committed in the Beatles lyrics, which he interpreted in his own way and read differently messages.

A brief analysis of the main components of the songs of Stabwound *Necrophagist* and *Your Tachchery Die With You*, by Dying Fetus, can read the usual musical components through which elements can be observed that warn of the existence of negative flu.

The singer who performs the vocal part of such a song, like many other artists of the same genre and hard rock genre, uses the technique of growling. It is about performing mostly quiet tones, with a throaty voice, with the intention of sounding rough, cutting, similar to the voice of animals, while wanting to express extremely strong emotions. Since the technique of singing is compared with the voice of animals, then their facial expression can also be compared.

4. Emotions and music

There is a difference between emotions and feelings and moods. Emotions are unconscious, while feelings of consciousness and upgrading of feelings caused by stimuli are instantaneous, a transient state, which can lead to mood swings, which unlike emotions, last longer and have a greater degree of influence on the mind.

Emotions are the answer to stimuli that stimulate centers in the brain and lead to psychological changes, and in order for someone to recognize them in stimuli like music, it is necessary to have a certain amount of empathy and emotional intelligence.

Brauer (2016) describes one situation of psychological harassment: "...The beginning of the war brought to Sachsenhausen the deportations of tens of thousands of people across Europe. In 1944, less than ten percent of prisoners were native German. Ignorance of German songs was enough to provoke punishment." Furthermore, Brauer (2016) explains that psychological abuse was an obligation of physical abuse, which would mean that everything happened through simultaneous physical abuse or forced physical activity of prisoners, such as marching, loud singing and simultaneous execution of push-ups and similar physical exertions. Prisoners would march more than thirty kilometres a day in inappropriate footwear, with cargo to transport, singing songs whose lyrics were a symbolic reflection of the situation they found themselves in, with pitiful messages.

The mere stay in concentration camps adversely affected the psyche of individuals. During the reign of the Greek military junta, the sound of a gong or motor vehicle was repeatedly played with torture to cover up screams of torture. Day and night there would be a loud sound of the engine hitting metal objects. That way, the prisoners weren't allowed to sleep. During all this time, the cries and cries of martyrs were clearly heard, which further instilled fear, while panicked conditions, mental disorders, healing and frightening situations and the inability to think realistically arose from the frequent and prolonged playing of these sounds

When people are constantly exposed to the same sounds or songs, these sounds and songs affect the mind on an unconscious level. So much negativity and emotional instability put prisoners in a state of despair and depression, which can worsen over time. The brain combines the elements offered to it into one whole, in other words, it connects visual, auditory and tactile images into one whole, that is, into a single feeling. Therefore, if a person observes another person's violence or is subjected to violent methods, hears screams and pain momentum and feels the same pain, the brain will generally perceive it as a negative effect that will manifest itself in mental health problems. This method was applied to prisoners: the unification of all negative elements into one whole, all for the purpose of harassment. It can be said that the whole process is well psychologically based. Music is systematically used to discipline and harass prisoners. "In the afternoon, somewhere outside there were a lot of beatings and I heard shouts from the martyrs. They turned up the speakers so the voices wouldn't be heard. The motive was a song I was going to go into the jungle with Tarzan. There was a song we listened to the whole time we weren't leaving. And a military policeman yelled, 'Wait your turn!' the wait was worse than a beating." Listening to the song, it was known what to expect, so it was a song that aroused fear and caused negative emotions due to the awareness of impending suffering. For days without water, tortured, listening to one and the same song, "Witness F" highlights the appearance of hallucinations: he saw the wall as a refrigerator with a drink, and security guards as family members. Music in such situations loses its original function of fun

and relaxation and becomes exclusively synonymous with terror and fear, and fear is precisely the sense of origin from which the amygdala is important, a structure in the limbic system of the brain that recognizes and expresses fear as feelings. Brauer (2016, 100) cites an important fact from the Auschwitz concentration camp about the existence of orchestras that played when Jewish prisoners arrived, knowing that they had been taken to gas chambers. The repertoire included classical compositions by famous composers, and the negative impact was seen in the fact that before arriving at the camp, musicians performed compositions with pleasure, out of love for music, in order to convey messages and emotions to the audience. But in this case, the act of playing itself is guided by completely contrasting reasons. Music no longer meant honor and pleasure to them, but indescribable fear and sadness. She's got a second function and as she remains etched for life. Members of the orchestra were rescued on the one hand because, thankfully, they were needed. "... new emotions appeared among the musicians, including anger, despair and shame. The stress was associated with the fear of failure in the eyes of the SS guards. These new negative emotions have been eashed on them and redefined the musician's connection to music. It is clear that music, with its strong connections to memory, emotions and identity, has the potential destroy the whole being..." The reason why identity matters when it comes to stimuli.

5. Conclusions

Music not only has positive effects on the human mind, but can also be negative. From the medical, psychological, philosophical, historical and musical aspects, many studies have been carried out and a lot of information has been collected about the negative impact of music on people's daily lives. EEG tests have shown that music, among other things, can cause emotions such as sadness, anxiety and fear, as well as mental and physical anxiety. From a medical point of view, it has been proven that the implementation of music therapy can be contraindicated in the mental states of patients and can change the therapeutic appearance in the direction of the negative. By studying this topic, we can shed light on the problems and consequences of epileptic seizures in musicogenic epilepsy and find out why some musical works in us cause tension and cause anxiety. The psychological aspect shows the impact of music on the brain during active or passive listening or making music and explains the ways in which the brain perceives sound stimuli and describes phenomena such as musical illusions.

Influence of hard rock, heavy and death metal music, with an emphasis on lyrics that further contribute to the negative impact on the human mind. Negative impact of this music on the behavior of young people. These types of music are often full of violent and suicidal lyrics. Listening to such music can cause mental disorders that can cause forced action, depression, anger and aggressive conditions. There are cases in which people with a predisposition to violent behavior have tried to commit suicide and inflict harm precisely because of the influence of songs whose lyrics combined with music and visual effects provoke their frustrations or anxiety states. From a historical point of view, emotions and the influence of music on them have been studied for centuries, and emotions will be at the heart of this work, because they are an important reflection of a person's mental state. Frequent listening to certain music in individuals promotes negative thinking or sad emotions, resulting in a worse state of the organism at the physiological and psychological level.

The brain is a center controlled by the organism, and the diagnostic method positron emission tomography shows which part of the brain is active during certain activities, including listening to certain music that provokes anti- and self-destructive behavior. Certain music stimulates negative thoughts and feelings, the harmful effect of certain volumes of music that has on the physiological and psychological aspect of a person is presented, with an emphasis on changes and hearing impairment.

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